

**INFLUENCE OF GENDER AND PERCEIVED SOCIAL SUPPORT ON
PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL BEING OF THE WIDOWED IN NORTHERN PLATEAU
STATE**

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ABSTRACT

Psychological wellbeing of the widowed based on influence of gender and perceived social support is the driving factor for this research. The study examined the influence of gender and perceived social support on psychological wellbeing of the widowed in northern Plateau State. A sample of 425 respondents participated in the study, and were drawn using purposive sampling technique. The design utilized for the study was a cross-sectional design and one (1) hypothesis was tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Result of the hypothesis revealed that there was no significant interaction influence of gender and perceived social support on the psychological wellbeing of the participants, mean scores of 12.59 ($SE = 1.98$), 15.21 ($SE = 1.09$), 15.16 ($SE = .92$) and 17.31 ($SE = .96$). The analysis yielded $F(1, 413) = .032, p = .858, \eta^2 < .001$. The implication of this study is that gender together with perceived social support will not interactively influence the psychological wellbeing of the widowed in northern Plateau State.

Key words: Gender, Perceived Social Support, Psychological Well Being, Widowed, Northern Plateau

INTRODUCTION

It is believed in contemporary society that gender and perceived social support have key significant influences on the psychological wellbeing of individuals, particularly the widows in Northern Plateau State. Gender is the social, psychological, and cultural aspects of being a male or female which has been divided into two categories, and individuals are considered one or the other (Haig, 2004; Maddux & Winstead 2019; Nadal, 2017; Sigelman & Rider, 2017). It can also be a biopsychosocial phenomenon, as it includes biological, social, psychological and behavioural aspects (Iantaffi, 2017; Knudson-Martin & Mahoney, 2009). Not all widowed men and women respond to the loss of a spouse in the same way because they differ in their perception, cognitive interpretation, and assessment of widowhood experience (Cardenal, Sanchez-Lopez & Ortiz-Tallo, 2005).

Perceived social support is paramount and essential factor in adjustment to bereavement on the emotional and mental health of the widowed, and the widowed are in need of social support from relatives, neighbours, colleagues, and bereaved peers as a particular type of social support (Hewitt, Turrell, & Giskes, 2010; Field & Schuldberg, 2011). Perceived social support by family and friends reduce the emotional and psychological distress of widowhood experience (Stroebe, Abakoumkin, & Stroebe, 2010). Low levels of social support are associated with increased loneliness, therefore widows lacking satisfying human relationships may find social support from significant others beneficial and helpful (Nalungwe, 2009).

Psychological wellbeing as the level of psychological happiness of an individual, with encompassed life satisfaction, and feeling of accomplishment is key, as it is the main element of mental health (Tang, Tang, & Gross, 2019). Psychological wellbeing consists of environmental mastery, autonomy, self-acceptance, positive relationships with other people, personal growth and development, and a feeling of purpose and meaning in life (Ryff, 1989). It is attained by achieving a state of balance affected by both challenging and rewarding life events (Dodge, Daly, Huyton, & Sanders, 2012; Muttaqin 2022).

The widowhood experienced by widowed men and women may differ, and there may be differences in the perception of social support among them. Kreider and Simmons (2003) posited that the probability of being widowed become high as men and women age, that is why over 33.33% of men in the United States from 85 years and above were widowed and almost 75% of women were also widowed in 2000 alone. Holden, Kim and Novak (2010)

confirmed that in 2002 50% of widowed men and women were below 74 years, and about 25% were below 64 years of age. Therefore, it should be noted that widowhood is not an event that occurs only at older age, but can also occur at younger age. Srivastava, Debnath, Shri, and Muhammad (2021) referred to widowhood as a traumatic event at any stage in life for the surviving partners with high repercussions on their physical, economical, and psychological well being, particularly in the first year of the loss of their spouses or rarely for a longer term. The experience of widowhood following the death of a spouse is personal, and is influenced by different factors like access to social support and psychological well being irrespective of gender.

In Europe and North American societies, widowhood is more common among women than men and the fact remains that women tend to marry men more than them or slightly older than them and men mostly die earlier than women explained this situation partially. The United States Bureau of Statistics (2008) revealed that globally, there are 7 million widowed women recorded yearly. In addition, the U.S. Census Bureau (2006) explained that in the United States in 2005, 18% of men and 52% of women ages 75 to 84 years were widowed; and 32% of men and 75 % of women ages 85 years and above were widowed. The Office for National Statistics (2005; 2006) confirmed in 2004 that in the United Kingdom alone, 16% of men and 45% of women from the age of 65 years and above were widowed. In the United States of America, women that were widowed account for the largest marital status among groups of women from age 65 years and above, with 42% while widowed men account for the second largest marital status group with 32% (U.S. Census Bureau, 2006) and they are broadly found similar to those in the United Kingdom (Office of National Statistics, 2005; 2006).

Potash (1986) reported that widowed women make up about 50% of the adult female population in Africa. Based on this report, there is a larger proportion of widowed women than men in Africa (Edewor & George, 2012). In the African region, 3% of all women from age 15 to 49 years are widowed, with more than 5% of ever-widowed women are under the age of 49 (Vande de Walle, 2016). In Nigeria, the rate of widowhood increases due to circumstances like banditry, insurgency, incessant attacks on communities, armed robbery, and flooding. Insurgency is peculiar to the North East, incessant attack on communities is peculiar to the North Central, and banditry is peculiar to the North-West. When a high death rate is recorded, then the level of social support received by widowed men and women from spirited individuals diminish, as some persons that might have provided social support to the

widowed might have died in the course of these ugly circumstances mentioned above. The Nigerian 1991 population census based on percentage distribution of population from 10 years and above by marital status indicated that 3.6 % were widowed. But when separated based on gender, it was discovered that widowed men made only 0.9% while widowed women made up 6.2% (National Population Commission, 1998). In addition, the 2006 population and housing census in Nigeria showed that the widows made up about 2% of the total population of those aged 10 years and above. But when separated by gender, 3.5% were female widowed whereas only 0.5% were widowed men. Therefore, the proportion of widowed men and women in Nigeria in 2006 was 230,609 and 1,693,692 respectively (National Population Commission, 2009).

Some studies showed gender differences in the level of psychological well-being (Nor-Ezdianie 2010; Akhter 2015; Fuller, Edwards, Vorakitphokatorn & Sermsri 2004; Gomez-Baya, Lucia-Casademunt & Salinas-Perez 2018). Perceived social support has positive relationship with the psychological well-being and also promote psychological well-being (Okawa, Yasuoka, Ishikawa, Poudel, Ragi, & Jimba 2011; Talwar, Kumaraswamy, & Mohd Fadzil 2013; Adyani, Ella, Safuwan, & Muryali 2019; Onuoha & Akintola 2018). Kafetsios (2007) reported that perceived social support was a predictor of psychological well-being outcomes in both males and females.

There is empirical evidence on gender, perceived social support and psychological wellbeing. Kafetsios (2007) in a study on gender, perceived social support and psychological well-being has been highlighted to see whether gender differences in functional aspects of social support such as support satisfaction, and structural aspects of social support like frequency of interactions with friends and relationship status exist, and if they exist, to what extent these influence the psychological well-being of males and females. Using hierarchy of regression analyses of cross-sectional data from Greek community samples, findings revealed that the functional aspect of social support was a predictor of psychological well-being outcomes in males, while structural aspects of social support were predictors of psychological well-being outcomes in females.

Glozah (2013) examined how academic stress and perceived social support influenced psychological well-being with particular reference to gender difference utilizing 226 participants comprising both males and females assessed based on perceived social support academic stress and psychological well-being. Results attributed partly to the socialisation role of gender indicate that perceived social support buffered the effects of academic stress on

psychological well-being, with female participants reported higher scores on perceived social support but reported poor psychological wellbeing while male respondents reported higher academic stress and better psychological well-being.

A comparative study was conducted by Shamin, Perveen, and Butt (2013) using a sample of 160 participants with 80 (40 males and 40 females) from nuclear families and 80 (40 males and 40 females) from extended families. They responded to perceived social support scale (Procidano & Heller, 1983) and psychological well-being scale (Ryff, 1989). Results revealed that there was a positive relationship between perceived social support and psychological well-being, female participants had more perceived social support and psychological well-being than males from both nuclear and extended families.

Kalpana (2016) studied to find out the association between perceived social support and psychological well-being among young working adults and to study gender differences in the relationship using a sample of 286 participants, with 173 (60.5%) males from the age bracket of 21 to 27 and a mean age of 23.51 years (SD 1.27), and 113 (39.5%) females with age range of 23.34 years (SD 1.27). Results indicated that perceived social support has a significant positive correlation with psychological well-being. Furthermore, significant gender differences were found in perceived social support, with females reported higher perceived social support than males. In addition, no significant gender differences were found in the psychological well-being of the participants.

Damilep, Gonkhir and Oyakose (2019) investigated the impact of gender and perceived social support on psychological well-being utilizing 200 participants with 104 (52.0%) males and 96 (48%) females, their ages ranging from 16 years to 31 years and above. Finding showed that there was no significant interaction effect of gender and perceived social support on the psychological well-being of study participants.

Siddiqui, Jahangir, and Hassan (2019) conducted a study in order to examine the value of perceived social support and psychological wellbeing among respondents based on gender differences using a sample of 562 participants (273 males and 289 females) with age ranges from 15 to 30 years. Participants were drawn from eight (8) top ranked public and private universities and degree awarding institutions of Pakistan in the metropolitan and cosmopolitan city of Karachi using convenient sampling techniques. Findings reported no significant gender distinction in perceived social support among participants, no significant difference in psychological well-being between males and female participants, and a significant negative correlation found between measures of perceived social support and

psychological well-being. Male participants showed low psychological well-being than their female counterparts with an established view that females receive higher social support than their male counterparts.

Onuoha and Tolulope (2021) evaluated gender and perceived social support on psychological well-being dimensions in older people using 242 participants drawn from selected communities in the South Western region of Nigeria, with 122 (50.4%) males and 120 (49.6%) females. The study reported that perceived social support had a significant effect on psychological well-being dimensions (personal growth and positive relationship with others), and also found significant interaction effects of gender and perceived social support on psychological well-being dimension (purpose in life). However, they concluded that gender and perceived social support have significant influence on psychological well-being of older persons.

Oyedele and Busari-Akinbode (2021) examined gender and perceived social support as correlates of psychological wellbeing among physically challenged university students in Nigeria. Results of the study showed significant differences in psychological wellbeing among the participants based on gender. Male participants revealed higher psychological wellbeing than female students who participated. Also, a significantly positive relationship was found between perceived social support and psychological wellbeing.

Muo (2022) investigated the roles of gender and perceived social support on psychological wellbeing among survivors of sexual assaults in Anambra State, Nigeria utilising 77 respondents using multiple regression. Results of the study indicated that gender did not play a significant role on psychological well being, but perceived social support significantly predicts psychological wellbeing of the participants. Yadav and Gupta (2024) study on perceived social support and psychological wellbeing among female partners of armed forces and non-armed forces indicated a significant positive relationship between perceived social support and psychological wellbeing. In addition, it was discovered that female respondents who were partners to military reported higher psychological well being than partners to civilians.

Hypothesis

1. There will be significant interaction effects of gender and perceived social support on psychological well being of the widowed in Northern Plateau State.

METHOD

Design

The study which sets out to examine the influence of gender and perceived social support (as independent variables) on psychological well-being (as dependent variable) employed a cross-sectional design.

Population

The study sample consisted of four hundred and twenty-five (N = 425) participants, comprising 147 (34.6%) males and 278 (65.4%) females with ages ranging from 20 to 85 years. They were purposively drawn from the six (6) Local Government Areas of Barkin Ladi, Bassa, Jos East, Jos North, Jos South, and Riyom that made up Plateau Northern Zone. This diverse representation enables a comprehensive exploration of gender, perceived social support and psychological wellbeing.

Sampling Technique

The study employed a purposive sampling technique as a method of sampling.

MEASURES

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS)

The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) developed by Zimet, Darlem, Zimet & Farley (1988) was used to collect data on perceived social support. The MSPSS is a 12 items instrument rated on a 7-point Likert-type scale ranging from “very strongly disagree” to “very strongly agree. This scale is meant to measure the perception of individuals on perceived social support, it demonstrates excellent internal consistency and test-retest reliability with Cronbach’s alpha of 0.92 to 0.94, and the finding supports the results of previous studies of the MSPSS (Zimet et al., 1988). There was an internal reliability investigation which used Cronbach’s alpha support earlier evaluation of MSPSS reliability (Zimet et al., 1988; Zimet, Powell, Farley, Werkman & Berkoff, 1990). The MSPSS validity has been established in a few populations where researchers have taken different approaches to validity testing among these populations (Mayo, 2015) and therefore, MSPSS’s stability overtime has been examined using the test-retest procedures.

To ascertain the construct validity and in determining the convergent validity of the MSPSS using a sample of 165 participants, factor analysis was carried out and findings revealed factor loadings of .413 - .770 for all the 12 items, indicating good factor extraction for the instrument items. Also, the reliability coefficient of the MSPSS was determined through internal consistency analysis providing the Cronbach alpha coefficient. The overall reliability coefficient for MSPSS was a Cronbach alpha of .863 (Damilep, 2022).

Psychological General Well-Being Index (PGWB-S) Short Version

The Psychological General Well-Being Index (PGWB-S) Short Version consists of six (6) items with six (6) options each, developed and validated by Grossi, Groth, Mosconi, Cerutti, Pace, Compare & Apolone (2006) was also used. The PGWBI which is a 22-item health-related Quality of Life (HRQoL) questionnaire developed in the United States produces an evaluation of self-perception of psychological well-being expressed by a score based on summary. The instrument has been validated and used in many countries on large samples of the general population and on specific patient groups. In addition, the overall questionnaires were administered to 1443 participants, but only 6 items were selected through a step-wise approach to describe 90% of the variance of the summary measure of the original questionnaire. The internal consistency showed high values of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient (range 0.80-0.92) for all three study samples, coming close to the value of the coefficient established for the original questionnaire (0.94).

Also, cross-validation in an independent sample of 755 cancer patients confirmed the item selection procedure and amount of variance explained by the new shorter questionnaire (ranging from 90.2 to 95.1 %, across strata of gender and age). The PGWB-S which is identified newly revealed good validity and acceptability for the use in various Italian settings (Grossi et al., 2006).

The reliability of the PGWB-S was determined through internal consistency analysis which provides the Cronbach alpha coefficient. The overall reliability coefficient for PGWB-S was a Cronbach alpha of .741. In determining the convergent validity of PGWB-S, factor analysis was carried out for the scale, and revealed factor loadings between .266 – .597 for all the 6 items (Damilep, 2022).

Procedure

The researchers sought for the consents of all participants before instruments of data collection were administered. Participation was voluntary and all ethical principles were followed. The researchers went to the study sites at different times and occasions. Data was collected among the widowed men and women across different communities of Plateau North Senatorial Zone. Only widowed men and women who met the inclusion criteria and consented to were administered questionnaires for data collection.

RESULTS

Descriptive Results

The section shows socio-demographic characteristics of participants, and descriptive statistics of participants consisting of mean, standard error, lower and upper bound scores. The socio-demographic characteristics of participants are shown in Table 1 while the mean, standard error, lower and upper bound scores are shown in Table 2.

Table 1
Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants

Socio-demographic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage %
Mean Age ± Standard Deviation	45.9±14	
Gender		
Male	147	34.6
Female	278	65.4
Age Range		
20-39 years	158	37.2
40-59 years	183	43.1
60-85 years	84	19.8
Occupation		
Civil servants	149	35.1
Business/Farming	181	42.6
Retirees	23	5.4
Students/Applicants	17	4.0
Dependents	55	12.9
Employment Status		
Employed	329	77.4
Unemployed	96	22.6
Local Government of Resident		
Barkin-Ladi	57	13.4
Bassa	45	10.6
Jos East	43	10.1
Jos North	122	28.7
Jos South	104	24.5
Riyom	54	12.7

Table 1 indicates that 278 (65.4%) of the participants were females while 147 (34.6%) were males. Among the study participants, 183 (43.1%) were from 40 to 49 years, 158 (37.2%) were from 20 to 39 years, and only 84 (19.8%) were from 60 to 85 years. Based on occupation, 181 (42.6%) were into businesses and farming, 149 (35.1) were civil servants, 55 (12.9%) were dependents, 23 (5.4%) were retirees and 17 (4.0%) were applicants/students. In terms of employment status, 329 (77.4%) participants were employed while only 96 (22.6%) were not employed. Among the participants, 122 (28.7%) were residents of Jos North, 104 (24.5%) were from Jos South, 57 (13.4%) were from Barkin-Ladi, 54 (12.7%) were from Riyom, 45 (10.6%) were from Bassa while 43 (10.1%) were from Jos East.

Table 2
Mean, Standard Error, Lower and Upper Bound Scores of Psychological Well Being across Gender and Perceived Social Support Interactions

Gender*PSS (Interaction)	Mean Psycho. Wellbeing	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper
Male*Low	12.59	1.98	8.70	16.49
Male*High	15.21	1.09	13.05	17.3
Female*Low	15.16	.92	13.33	17.002
Female*High	17.31	.96	15.43	19.19

Table 2 is the presentation of mean, standard error, lower bound score and upper bound score of psychological well being based on gender and perceived social support interactions. Male participants who reported low perceived social support demonstrated a mean psychological well being score of 12.59 ($SE = 1.98$), indicating a lower level of psychological wellbeing within this group. Contrarily, male widowed participants reporting high perceived social support had a higher mean score of 15.21 ($SE = 1.09$), meaning a significantly improved psychological wellbeing. Among female widowed participants, those with low perceived social support revealed a mean psychological wellbeing score of 15.16 ($SE = 0.92$), confirming moderate psychological well being. In contrast, female participants reporting high perceived social support had the highest mean score at 17.31 ($SE = 0.96$), signifying better psychological wellbeing. The 95% confidence intervals emphasize that these distinctions are reliable, demonstrating a high level of confidence in the variations observed. Female participants with high perceived social support revealed highest levels of psychological well being.

Inferential Results

Result of the hypothesis tested is presented in this section.

Table 3
ANOVA Summary Table for Gender and Perceived Social Support on Psychological well being

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Effect size
Corrected Model	799.440	11	72.676	2.785	.002	.069
Intercept	13704.058	1	13704.05	525.201	.000	.560

Gender * PSS	.832	1	.832	.032	.858	<.001
Error	10776.409	413	26.093			
Total	94652.000	425				
Corrected Total	11575.849	424				

Table 3 provides ANOVA table results for the hypothesis tested. Findings of the hypothesis indicated no significant interaction effect of gender and perceived social support on the psychological wellbeing of the widowed, with means, 12.59 ($SE = 1.98$), 15.21 ($SE = 1.09$), 15.16 ($SE = .92$), 17.31 ($SE = .96$), $F(1, 413) = .032, p = .858. \eta^2 < .001$. The effect size value of $< .001$ indicates that the interaction of gender and perceived social support accounts for $< .1\%$ of the variance in psychological wellbeing among the study participants. Hypothesis is not supported.

DISCUSSION

Results of the hypothesis revealed that there was no significant interaction effect of gender and perceived social support on psychological wellbeing among the widowed. The result is in line with the findings of Damilep et al (2019) which reported no significant interaction effect of gender and perceived social support on psychological well being. In a related finding, Siddiqui et al (2019) confirmed that no significant gender difference was found in perceived social support among participants. Also, they reported that no significant difference in psychological well-being was found between males and females. However, Siddiqui, et al (2019) findings also showed significant negative correlation between measures of perceived social support and psychological well-being. Moreover, male participants showed lower psychological well-being than their female counterparts with an established view that females receive higher social support from family, friends and significant others than males.

Contrarily, gender and perceived social support have been found to be influential in determination of psychological well being among participants (Onuoha & Tolulope, 2021). This is because a significant interaction effect of gender and perceived social support on psychological wellbeing was reported. Slight findings were posited by Kafetsios (2007) study which indicated that structural aspects of perceived social support were predictors of psychological wellbeing outcomes in females, whereas functional aspects of perceived social

support were determinants of psychological wellbeing outcomes in males. Furthermore, it has been discovered that female participants had more social support and better psychological well being than their male counterparts from nuclear and extended families (Shamin et al, 2013). Kalpana (2016) showed that perceived social support had a significant positive correlation with psychological well being, but no significant gender differences in the psychological wellbeing of participants were found.

CONCLUSION

Drawing from the outcome of this research, there was no significant interaction effect of gender and perceived social support on psychological well being of the study participants. Therefore, the finding of the study has far-reaching implications, as this study provided stronger awareness of the non-interactive implications of gender and perceived social support on the psychological wellbeing of the widowed. Based on this finding, the researchers recommend that the non-significant interactive effect of gender and perceived social support on the psychological wellbeing of the widowed is a call for more investigation to be carried out in this area of study. Therefore, addressing the non-significant role of gender and perceived social support, there should be adoption of a comprehensive approach to enhance the psychological wellbeing of the widowed.

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